

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 124

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 124

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 124:0 A Song of Ascents, of David.</p> <p>Psa. 124:1 “Had it not been the LORD who was on our side,” ^bLet Israel now say, ² “Had it not been the LORD who was on our side When men rose up against us, ³ Then they would have “swallowed us alive, When their ^banger was kindled against us; ⁴ Then the “waters would have engulfed us, The stream would have ¹swept over our soul; ⁵ Then the “raging waters would have ¹swept over our soul.”</p> <p>Psa. 124:6 Blessed be the LORD, Who has not given us ¹to be “torn by their teeth. ⁷ Our soul has ^aescaped ^bas a bird out of the ‘snare of the trapper; The snare is broken and we have escaped. ⁸ Our ^ahelp is in the name of the LORD, Who ^bmade heaven and earth.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 124:1 שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלוֹת לְדָוִד לְדָוִד</p> <p>יְהוָה שְׁתַּיִּחַ לָנוּ יֹאמְרוּ-נָא יִשְׂרָאֵל : ² לְדָוִד יְהוָה שְׁתַּיִּחַ לָנוּ בְּקִוּיָם עָלֵינוּ אָדָם : ³ אֲזִי תִיַּיִם בְּלַעֲוֵנוּ בַּחֲרוֹת אִפְסֵם בָּנוּ : ⁴ אֲזִי הַמַּיִם שְׁטַפוּנוּ נִחַלָה עָבַר עַל-נַפְשֵׁנוּ : ⁵ אֲזִי עָבַר עַל-נַפְשֵׁנוּ הַמַּיִם הַיָּדוֹנִים : ⁶ בְּרוּךְ יְהוָה שֶׁלֹּא נִתְּנָנוּ לְטָרֶף לְשִׁנֵּיהֶם : ⁷ נַפְשֵׁנוּ כַּצֶּפֶר נִמְלְטָה מִכַּף יוֹקְשֵׁים הַכַּף נִשְׁבַּר וַאֲנִתָּנוּ נִמְלְטָנוּ : ⁸ עֲזָרָנוּ בְּשֵׁם יְהוָה לַעֲשֵׂה שָׁמַיִם וָאָרֶץ :</p>

References

Psalm 124:1

^aPs 94:17

^bPs 129:1

Psalm 124:3

^aNum 16:30; Ps 35:25; 56:1; 57:3; Prov 1:12

^bGen 39:19; Ps 138:7

Psalm 124:4

¹Or *passed over*

^aJob 22:11; Ps 18:16; 32:6; 69:2; 144:7

Psalm 124:5

¹Or *passed over*

^aJob 38:11

Psalm 124:6

¹Lit *as a prey to*

^aPs 27:2; Prov 30:14

Psalm 124:7

^aPs 141:10; 2 Cor 11:33; Heb 11:34

^bProv 6:5

^cPs 91:3; Hos 9:8

Psalm 124:8

^aPs 121:2

^bGen 1:1; Ps 134:3

Targum

Psa. 124:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss, composed by David. Had it not been for the LORD who was our help – let Israel say now – ² Had it not been for the word of the LORD who was our help, when a son of man rose against us – ³ Then they would have swallowed us while alive, when their anger grew strong against us. ⁴ Then the waters would have washed us away, sickness would have passed over our soul. ⁵ Then the king would have passed over our soul, he who is likened to the malicious waters of the sea. ⁶ Blessed is the name of the LORD, who has not handed us over as dead meat to their teeth. ⁷ Our soul is like a bird saved from the traps of the fowlers; the trap broke, and we have been saved. ⁸ Our help is in the name of the word of the LORD, who made heaven and earth.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The Psalmist offers thanksgiving to the LORD for all His assistance for the Children of Israel. Israel has survived throughout the centuries despite her enemy's attempts to destroy her. In every generation an enemy of the LORD's people arose who tried to crush the soul of the holy nation. In every case the LORD's people have had victory from the Sefirah Netzach. In this Psalm the nations are compared to deep water. This water can drown people or can become strong enough to sweep enemies away.

Notes on the Psalm

Too many people today believe that everything good that has happened to them in life is by their control alone. Indeed, the LORD has given us freewill. Therefore, our individual choices help drive our lives. However, the LORD will give us small nudges from time to time to drive our souls to a specific situation. Certain events occur which we call coincidence are not that but intentional pressures from the LORD. The question becomes, will the person react positively or ignore the nudge? That is the freewill part of the equation.

The saying is "when God closes a door, He opens a window." It is up to the person to see the window open and to take advantage of it. Randomness in the world will cause unexpected events to occur. When bad things happen, will you place your faith that the LORD will offer a nudge to greener pastures? If you acknowledge this fact, then you will be better off in life.

Look for the nudges from the LORD. The Shekinah is always with us transferring the LORD's wishes to us. Learn to listen for the voice of the Shekinah calling out to you. In such a busy and noisy world people tend to forget to listen.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

